

Optimizing Blood Utilization: A Comprehensive Cross-Sectional Study on Patterns, Quality Indicators, and Wastage Rates in a Tertiary Care Hospital

A. Preetha¹, Anitha T.², S. Sara³, P. Parameshwari⁴

¹Post-Graduate Resident, Department of Community Medicine, Chengalpattu Medical College, Tamil Nadu, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Transfusion Medicine, Chengalpattu Medical College, Tamil Nadu, India

³A.R. Hospital, Ramanathapuram, Tamil Nadu, India

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Chengalpattu Medical College, Tamil Nadu, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. S. Sara

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Abstract:

Background & Objectives: Blood transfusion is an essential aspect of patient care, particularly in the inpatient and emergency settings. This study estimates the blood utilization rate, wastage factor, and quality indicators in a tertiary care hospital.

Materials and Methods: The present study was a retrospective record-based cross-sectional study conducted in a tertiary teaching hospital. The data was collected from January 1st to December 31st 2022, from the blood issue register, cross-matching register, blood group register, and transfusion reaction register respectively. The department-wise and overall utilization of blood and its components, the blood quality indicators like cross-match: transfusion ratio (C: T), Transfusion probability (%T), Transfusion Index (TI), Transfusion reaction rate, and wastage rate were analyzed.

Results: Among 9,930 units, the utilization rate reached 100%, with packed red blood cells (PRBC) being the most prevalent at 58.94% and cryoprecipitate at the lowest with 1.04%. In terms of departmental usage, Obstetrics and Gynecology (OG) led with 35.5%, while orthopedics had the lowest usage at 4.2%. Key blood quality indicators yielded a C: T ratio of 0.99%, %T at 84.08%, TI at 1.00%, a transfusion reaction rate of 0.17% and, a wastage rate of 0.18%.

Interpretation & Conclusion: Our study indicates effective blood utilization, as evidenced by positive outcomes in all blood quality indicators. Blood banks play a crucial role in vigilantly monitoring the trends and maintaining blood utilization in life-saving needs.

Keywords: Blood quality indicators, Blood utilization, Transfusion reactions, Utilization rate, Wastage rate.

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Introduction

Blood transfusion is essential to healthcare services and remains the mainstay of treatment in various clinical conditions.[1] The primary responsibility of blood transfusion services is to utilize the donated blood efficiently and to provide a safe, sufficient, and timely supply of blood and blood products.[1]

As per the World Health Organization (WHO), a blood donation rate of 1% of the population is commonly considered the minimum threshold to fulfill a nation's fundamental blood requirements. [2,3]

However, significant disparities persist in the evaluation of demand, supply, and utilization of

blood and its derivatives. [2,3] This study comprehensively analyses blood utilization patterns, quality indicators, wastage rates, and transfusion reactions within a tertiary care hospital environment.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Data Collection: A one-year retrospective and cross-sectional design was conducted, covering the period from January 1st to December 31st, 2022. The data was collected from a tertiary center teaching hospital, focusing on various aspects of the study from blood and its components. Official permission from the

institution was obtained before collecting data from registers, including the blood issue register, cross-matching register, blood group register, and transfusion reaction register. This methodical approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of blood management within the specified timeframe and healthcare setting.

Data Analysis: The study involves a sample size of 9,930 transfusions, categorized into distinct blood components, including whole blood, packed red blood cells (PRBC), fresh frozen plasma (FFP), platelets, and cryoprecipitate. This comprehensive approach enables an in-depth examination of how each component is utilized, conducting a detailed analysis of blood utilization patterns within each specific category.

Additionally, the analysis extended to departmental variations, and this unravelled distinct patterns in blood component utilization across the various departments. Transfusion reaction rate and overall wastage rate of the blood were estimated in the study. Quality indicators of the blood were analyzed by evaluating with relevant parameters, to provide a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness and safety of transfusion practices in the hospital. The study parameters included whole blood and blood component usage, transfusion reactions, wastage of blood and blood products, and the average turnaround time for issues of blood and blood components.

Quality Indicators [QI]

Blood utilization in our study was computed using the following indices.

1. Cross-match to transfusion ratio (C/T ratio = number of units cross-matched/ number of units transfused).[2]
2. Transfusion probability (%T) = number of patients transfused/number of patients cross-matched $\times 100$.[2]
3. Transfusion index (TI) = number of units transfused/number of patients cross-matched.[2]
4. Transfusion reactions = Number of transfusion reactions $\times 100$ /number of transfusions.[4]

5. Wastage rate = number of blood and blood products discarded or wasted $\times 100$ /number of blood and blood products intended from blood bank.[4]

Statistical Analysis: The data was presented as frequency and percentages, depicted through bars and graphs. Quality indicators are computed using standard formulas. Data was analyzed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS software, including Version 28 (Released 2021; IBM Corp., Armonk, New York, United States).

Results

In 2022, among the 9,930 transfusions, packed red blood cells (PRBCs) accounted for 58.94% (5853 transfusions) of the total, emphasizing their significant utilization. In contrast, cryoprecipitate constituted a smaller proportion, representing only 1.04% (103 transfusions), as depicted in Figure 1. Further examination of blood groups revealed a distinct preference, the most utilized, while AB negative held a more reserved position. Notably, a 100% utilization rate for all blood and components signifies the hospital's efficient resource management.

The Platelet-Rich Plasma Concentrate (PRPC) emerged as the most extensively used blood component, reaching a peak utilization of 600 units in March. In contrast, cryoprecipitate exhibited minimal usage, with only one unit recorded in July. This trend is visually represented in Figure 2, illustrating the varying utilization of blood components throughout 2022.

Table 1 provides insights into the utilization of blood and blood components across different departments. The Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology stands out, utilizing a significant 35.4% (3514 blood transfusions) of blood and blood components within the broader context of departmental blood utilization.

From Table 2, the transfusion reaction rate is recorded at 0.17% with a low wastage rate of 0.18%, indicating an efficient utilization of blood resources. The commonly reported transfusion reactions include fever, chills, rash, and urticaria.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Blood Component Utilization across Departments.

Department	WB (%)	PRBC (%)	FFP (%)	Platelet (%)	Cryo (%)	Overall (%)
Medicine	169 (17.2)	904 (15.4)	562 (25.9)	303 (36.4)	15 (14.4)	19.6%
Surgery	190 (19.4)	1195 (20.4)	475 (21.9)	98 (11.7)	2 (1.9)	19.7%
OG	200 (20.4)	2573 (43.9)	560 (25.8)	108 (12.9)	84 (80.7)	35.4%
Pediatrics	41 (4.1)	378 (6.4)	152 (7)	229 (27.5)	0 (0)	8%
TAEI	315 (32.2)	485 (8.2)	380 (17.5)	90 (10.8)	3 (2.8)	12.8%
Orthopedics	62 (6.3)	318 (5.4)	35 (1.6)	4 (0.4)	0 (0)	4.2%
Total	977	5853	2164	832	104	9930

[WB- Whole Blood; PRBC- Packed Red Blood Cell Count; FFP- Fresh Frozen Plasma; Cryo- Cryoprecipitate, OG- Obstetrics and Gynecology; TAEI- Tamil Nadu accident emergency and care initiative]

Table 2: Quality Indicators for Blood Transfusion.

Quality Indicators	Value	Reference value
Cross-match to transfusion ratio = $\frac{\text{No. of units cross-matched}}{\text{No. of units transfused}}$	0.99%	<2.5
Transfusion probability = $\frac{\text{No. of units transfused}}{\text{No. of patients cross matched}} \times 100$	84.08%	50%
Transfusion Index = $\frac{\text{No. of units transfused}}{\text{No. of patients cross matched}} \times 100$	1.00 %	≥ 0.5
Transfusion Reaction Rate = $\frac{\text{No. of transfusion reactions}}{\text{No. of transfusions}} \times 100$	0.17%	-
Wastage rate = $\frac{\text{No. of blood units discarded}}{\text{No. of blood units issued}} \times 100$	0.18%	-

Figure 1: Blood Component Utilization in Hospital Transfusions
 PRBC: Packed Red Blood Cell, FFP: Fresh Frozen Plasma, CRYO: Cryoprecipitate

Figure 2: Trend Analysis of Blood Component Utilization
 PRBC: Packed Red Blood Cell, FFP: Fresh Frozen Plasma, CRYO: Cryoprecipitate

Discussion

Blood and blood components play a vital role in a patient's care.[2] The limited supply of this vital resource comes with considerable risks, such as infections and reactions.[2] The utilization patterns of blood and its components, as well as the status of transfusion practices, vary across different centers and countries.[2]

A study showed that the majority of the blood transfused was whole blood (50.4%) which was contrary to the present study.[5] In the present study, it was found that the majority of the blood component transfused was PRBC (58.94%) followed by FFP. The least number of transfused blood components was cryoprecipitate (1.04%). Furthermore, our analysis highlighted that the highest proportion of transfused blood units exhibited O positive, while the least prevalent was AB negative, emphasizing the distribution patterns within the study.

The blood bank plays a crucial role in meeting the demand for this life-saving product while concurrently analyzing and appraising existing trends in blood ordering.[6] In our study, we observed a remarkable 100% total utilization rate in our hospital encompassing 9,930 transfusions. A comparative analysis with another study by Mondal T et al [2] revealed a utilization rate of 78.95%. Therefore, the present study revealed a better utilization rate.

Across all departments, PRBC was the most common choice among the various transfusions. Comparing the overall percentages, Obstetrics and Gynecology utilized the highest at 35.4%, while orthopedics had the lowest utilization at 4.2%. In contrast, an alternate study reported higher orthopedic usage of 20.1%.[6] This variance underscores discrepancies in departmental blood utilization practices observed across different hospitals.[6]

Quality indicators (QIs) serve as a tool within the Quality Management System (QMS) and their purpose extends beyond merely demonstrating the existing level of quality performance within the organization.[7] Several indices are employed to evaluate the effectiveness of the blood ordering and utilization system.[8]

The cross-match to transfusion ratio stands as an important quality indicator for blood ordering and utilization, evaluating the appropriateness of pretransfusion test ordering and enabling benchmarking between departments and hospitals.[9] In our study, the overall cross-match to transfusion (C/T) ratio stands at 0.99% indicating efficient blood usage (Reference value <2.5%).[2] In comparison, a separate study reported an overall C/T ratio of 1.27%.[2] The

lower ratio in our study suggests a more optimized and reasonable approach to blood transfusion practices, aligning with the established reference values.

In our study, the transfusion probability (%T) stands notably high at 84.08 where higher is considered appropriate (Reference value 50%).[2] However, it is essential to note that Belayneh T et al.,[8] suggest a threshold of 30% and above as appropriate in 2013.[2] In comparison, a study by Mondal B et al [2] reports a T% of 67.52%, highlighting differences in transfusion probability standards across studies.[2]

The transfusion index (TI) in the current study was 1%, exceeding the reference value of 0.5% and higher.[2] Another study by Mondal et al [2] and Belayneh T et al [8] also reports a similar transfusion index of 0.92% and 0.77%, which suggests effective blood utilization. Therefore, the overall ratio of C: T, %T, and TI index are considered to be optimal as compared with the standard values.[2,8,10] Percentage (%) of transfusion reactions, which is defined as any adverse reaction to the transfusion of blood or blood components that may range from an allergic reaction to a life-threatening complication such as transfusion-related acute lung injury (TRALI) and graft versus host disease (GVHD).[4] In the current study, the transfusion reaction rate stands at 0.17%, with chills, rigors, rash, and urticaria emerging as the most prevalent reactions.

In a distinct study from 2011, a non-hemolytic transfusion reaction occurred in 1 out of 16 patients, constituting 6.25% due to a mismatch.[4] The concern surrounding the wastage of blood and blood products is of substantial importance.[11] Implementing vigilant monitoring practices and introducing corrective measures to target underlying issues in the production and storage of blood components has proven effective in mitigating wastage.[12]

The data obtained from the institution's blood bank revealed a low wastage rate of 0.18%. When compared with other studies, a European study spanning 10 countries reported a wastage range of 0.2% to 7.7%, averaging 4.5%.[13] Conversely, the study conducted by Mondal et al, [2] revealed a significantly higher wastage rate of 21.05%. The comparatively low wastage rate of 0.18% in this analysis indicates efficient blood utilization, contrasting with instances where higher wastage rates may signify less effective blood management. To reduce the wastage rate of blood and blood components, incorporating a hemovigilance system into the blood transfusion service would enhance the efficient monitoring of transfusions, thereby contributing to the reduction of waste for limited blood and blood products.[12]

Our study has a few limitations. The retrospective design restricts the depth and scope of the investigation. The transfusion reaction rate, a key metric for assessing blood safety, relies solely on reported reactions. This may introduce a bias as not all reactions may be reported.

The potential underreporting of transfusion reactions is a concern, affecting the accuracy of the observed reaction rate. Additionally, the study lacks department-specific wastage rates, offering only an overall wastage rate. These limitations are crucial to consider when interpreting the study's findings, guiding future research in this field.

Conclusion

This study emphasizes efficient blood utilization, demonstrated by minimal wastage rates and 100% effective blood component utilization. The comprehensive analysis of blood quality indicators further solidifies the evidence supporting effective blood management practices. Quality laboratory practices significantly impact diagnosis and patient care, as many diagnoses rely on laboratory tests. Addressing the universal issue of blood wastage in hospitals requires easy and cost-effective interventions.

Implementing a structured blood transfusion policy, facilitated by hospital administration through regular audits, adherence to standard transfusion guidelines, and clinical programs with periodic feedback, can significantly reduce the over-ordering of blood. This approach minimizes unnecessary compatibility testing, the return of unused blood, and wastage due to expiration.

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